

CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER (CFRP) COMPOSITES WITH A DISCRETE AND OPTIMISED SELF-HEALING FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

A novel, fully integrated single capsule healing system for application in carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites is demonstrated. Microcapsules, containing epoxy resin (EPON 828) and organic solvent (ethyl phenylacetate) were decorated with a selected catalytic curing agent (scandium (III) triflate) and embedded in an epoxy based unidirectional composite (SE 70 carbon/epoxy, Gurit UK). Epoxy containing capsules were prepared by *in-situ* polymerisation in an oil-in-water emulsion, where the catalyst was impregnated onto their rough polymeric surface using an incipient wetness technique. Prior to implementation in a composite, the system was investigated for its activity using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and for adhesion promotion between two microscopic slides. The released epoxy resin undergoes ring opening polymerization (ROP) upon contact with the curing agent, and subsequently bonds two glass surfaces together. The proof of concept studies revealed that the developed system is active after synthesis and exhibited significant potential to be implemented as a self-healing material. The curing time was also dependent on the catalyst load on the microcapsule surface. The healing efficiency was quantified using double cantilever beam (DCB) test specimens containing the single component system and the dispersed separately capsule – catalyst system, in a region of controlled crack propagation. A 10-15% healing recovery is reported for both investigated systems. The encapsulated resin formulation with Sc(OTf)₃ at catalytic ratio was also used for manual healing of DCB specimens and resulted in a 52% recovery of initial fracture toughness. Low healing efficiency was associated with low availability of Sc(OTf)₃ necessary for polymerisation to take place, it is possible that premature catalyst consumption occurred during composite processing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are becoming the most commonplace in aerospace, automotive, marine and offshore structures [1]. Composites subjected to service conditions are susceptible to damage, such as matrix cracking, crack propagation and delaminations between plies, which if undetected and unrepaired, can be of a significant detriment to material performance. Structures designed to heal spontaneously offer a solution to often complicated and costly damage detection methods and manual repairs [2,3]. In the most developed approach to self-healing, a monomer is encapsulated in a polymeric shell and embedded in the host matrix materials [5]. Microcapsules are ruptured by a propagating crack that release the healing chemistries. Upon subsequent chemical reaction or physicochemical processes, a new polymeric network bonds the delaminated surfaces together and restores material integrity [2-4].

In this research, a fully integrated system based on an encapsulated epoxy resin - catalyst approach is demonstrated. Microcapsules containing diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (75wt%) and the high boiling point organic solvent, ethyl phenylacetate (25wt%) were documented in previous studies as effective in the application of self-healing epoxides [6]. Scandium (III) triflate (Sc(OTf)₃)

was selected as the suitable initiator due to its stability and catalytic activity in polymerising epoxy resins [6,7]. Furthermore, scandium (III) triflate embedded in a CFRP composite was previously demonstrated to remain active in repeated healing *via* microvascular channels [7].

Herein, scandium (III) triflate, was supported on the microcapsules surface using an incipient wetness technique. The integrated system was evaluated for its activity and healing performance. Catalyst was impregnated at catalytic load and measured relatively to the mass of epoxy resin in the range of catalytic ratio. The system activity was investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Additionally, a fully integrated system was embedded into a modified double cantilever beam (DCB) coupon test specimen geometry and tested in mode I to evaluate healing performance. The aim of this study was to demonstrate a fully integrated microcapsular self-healing system in a high performance composite material. The results collected here have shown that the 'one shot' system is stable and active after synthesis. However, less than 15% recovery of composite properties was achieved for the novel integrated system and traditional system utilizing catalyst particles dispersed in polymer.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Materials for microencapsulation and incipient wetness: Ethyl phenylacetate (EPA, $C_6H_5CH_2C(O)OC_2H_5$), urea (NH_2CONH_2), poly(ethylene-*alt*-maleic anhydride) (EMA, $M_w=100,000-500,000$, powder); resorcinol ($C_6H_4-1,3-(OH)_2$), formalin (formaldehyde, 37 wt% in H_2O , CH_2O), ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl) and scandium (III) triflate ($Sc(OTf)_3$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was purchased from Fisher Scientific. Commercial epoxy resin - EPON 828 was purchased from PolySciences, Inc.

Materials for composite manufacturing: Carbon fiber/epoxy resin tape (SE 70) and adhesive resin film (SA 70) were sourced from Gurit, UK and also used as received.

2.2 Microencapsulation

Microcapsules containing epoxy resin and organic solvent were prepared by *in-situ* polymerisation in an oil-in-water emulsion [8]. Briefly, 60 mL of water phase containing 1 wt% of emulsion stabilizer (EMA) was prepared in a round bottomed vessel and subsequently 1.25 g of urea, 0.125 g of Resorcinol and 0.125 g of ammonium chloride were added and dissolved. After that, the pH of the water phase was adjusted by dropwise addition of NaOH (≈ 0.2 N) to 3.10. Stirring speed was increased to 800 rpm and 30 mL of measured oil phase was added dropwise. 3.16 g of formalin was added and temperature was increased to 55°C. After 4 hours, the stirrer was stopped, and the microcapsule slurry was left in the water medium for 24 hours at room temperature. Next, microcapsules were filtered in order to separate capsules with desired size. Capsules were vacuum filtered and rinsed a few times with ethanol/water. The isolated capsules were post heated at 55°C in an oven for 2 days. Yield of microcapsules was calculated relatively to mass of used materials (Y%).

2.3 Microcapsules analysis

Microcapsules diameter and size distribution was analyzed by a Zeiss optical microscope AX10, Imager.M2 equipped with a video camera AxioCam.ICc 1. For the size distribution, image analysis software (ImageJ) was used. Mean diameter and size distribution were obtained from at least 500 measurements of capsule diameter. Surface morphology analysis for dry microcapsules and for capsules impregnated with the $Sc(OTf)_3$ catalyst was performed with a scanning electron microscope JOEL SEM 5600LV. Thermal resistance of microcapsules was determined using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Mass loss of microcapsules was recorded during non-isotherm from 25 to 500°C and isothermal measurements at using a TA Instruments Q500 TGA.

2.4 Impregnation of poly(urea-formaldehyde) microcapsules with Sc(OTf)₃ catalyst

The catalytic curing agent was supported on the microcapsule surface using an incipient wetness technique [9]. The required amount of Sc(OTf)₃ was dissolved in a volume of deionized water corresponding to the pore volume of the rough capsule surface. The volume of pore size was quantified by measuring water needed to completely wet dry capsules. The solution was added dropwise to the dry support during gentle mixing and immediately dried for 5 hour at 45°C.

2.5 Tests for activity of fully integrated systems

All prepared specimens were tested qualitatively for adhesion between two glass microscopic slides prior to DSC analysis. A few milligrams of microcapsules was placed on one glass slide and covered with the second. Capsules were crushed and glass slides were clamped. Specimens were left at 80°C for curing of the released resin and tested every 60 minutes for adhesion. Differential scanning calorimetry was performed for crushed microcapsules decorated with 10 pph of the catalyst. DSC was performed using TA Instruments Q200 DSC from 0 - 250°C at a modulated heating rate of 10°C/min and constant flow of purge gas (N₂).

2.6 Composite manufacturing

Composites with embedded healing chemistries were manufactured using unidirectional carbon/epoxy resin tape (SE 70, Gurit UK) and adhesive resin film (SA 70, Gurit, UK) by standard hand-lay up technique (16 plies – 80 mm x 195 mm). Laminates after lay-up were sealed on an aluminium tool plate and consolidated according to the manufacturer's recommendations (at 100°C for 100 minutes) under vacuum of 660-710 mmHg. The artificially created damage region was filled with a resin paste (SA70 resin film) containing healing chemistries at the desired weight load (Table 2). The filling paste was prepared by dispersion of dry capsules and/or catalyst at 65°C. Each panel was equipped with a release film at 85 mm from the edge of specimens overlapping at minimum 500 µm of the resin pocket. The detailed configuration of the system is presented in the Figure 1. After curing, composite plates were removed from the vacuum bag and a 30 mm region from the panel front was grit blasted. Composite plates were then trimmed and cut into DCB specimens (20 mm x 175 mm). Piano hinges were bonded to the specimens at the pre-cracked end using Araldite 2014 structural adhesive and left at room temperature until fully cured.

2.7 Mode I tests and self-healing quantification

A standard test machine (Shimadzu AGX-X) equipped with 1 kN load cell and a video camera was used in opening mode I interlamianr fracture tests for virgin and healed double cantilever beam tests specimens (DCB). Tests were performed in accordance to the ASTM 5528-01 standard method [10]. Specimens were tested in crack opening mode at 3 mm/min displacement rate, from the release film to the end of resin rich region containing microcapsules. Afer testing, specimens were unloaded, sealed and left at 80°C for 24 hours. Healed specimens were retested using the same methodology.

Healing efficiencies (η) were determined for all autonomous and manually healed speciemns using the initial (P_{initial}) and healed (P_{healed}) peak fracture loads. The influence of resin rich region on the materials attribute and the effect of microcapsules was determined by calculating the critical mode I strain energy release rates, G_{IC} , values in accordance with the ASTM 5528-01 standard [10].

Figure 1: CFRP double cantilever beam specimen (DCB) geometry containing artificially created damage region with embedded self-healing chemistries.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Microencapsulation of epoxy resin and organic solvent

Microcapsules containing the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) were synthesized using *in-situ* polymerisation in an oil-in-water emulsion [8]. Size distribution and corresponding scanning electron micrographs are presented in Figure 2. Capsules exhibited a wide size distribution ranging from 20-420 microns in diameter. The yield of microencapsulation was calculated as 95%.

Figure 2: Size distribution of prepared poly(urea-formaldehyde) microcapsules containing 75wt% of epoxy resin (EPON 828) and 25wt% of organic solvent (Ethyl phenylacetate – EPA) and corresponding SEM image.

The thermal stability of microcapsules was determined using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Non – isothermal analysis indicated that microcapsules are stable up to 170°C where the associated mass loss corresponds on evaporation of microcapsule solvent (ethyl phenylacetate, bp. 229°C) and decomposition of DGEBA resin. Isothermal analysis indicated that microcapsules are stable when exposed to elevated temperature and the associated 2.5% weight loss corresponds to water evaporation from the polymeric shell. Results of thermal stability indicated that capsules containing epoxy resin and organic solvent are thermally stable and should stay intact during the curing process of selected carbon fibre/epoxy resin tape (SE 70 Carbon/epoxy).

Figure 3: Representative TGA traces for the microcapsules containing epoxy resin; non-isothermal analysis; isothermal analysis.

3.2 Impregnation of Sc(OTf)₃ on microcapsules surface and activity tests

Dry poly(urea-formaldehyde) microcapsules were impregnated with a water solution of Sc(OTf)₃ using an incipient wetness technique [9]. Specimens were prepared at four loadings of catalyst, calculated relatively to the microcapsules mass (FI - 1, FI - 2.5, FI - 5.0 and FI - 10). From SEM analysis (Figure 4) it was observed that capsules are stable after processing and that the rough surface was uniformly covered with a precipitate of catalyst. The qualitative tests for adhesion at elevated temperature revealed that the system remained active after the impregnation step and the released epoxy resin-organic solvent polymerised in contact with the supported Sc(OTf)₃. Glass slides were adhesively bonded once the microcapsules were crushed and exposed to 80°C for 1 hour for the highest supported catalyst loading. This results indicated that the time of curing of released epoxy is dependent on the catalyst loading supported on the microcapsules.

Table 1: Designation and initial tests for adhesion promotion at 80 °C of the fully integrated capsule – catalyst system.

Designation	Catalyst load *	Epoxy resin location	Adhesion promotion					
			1h	2h	3h	4h	5h	24h
Control	3.25	Liquid	-	X	X	X	X	X
FI - 1	1	Microcapsules	-	-	-	-	-	X
FI - 2.5	2.5		-	-	-	X	X	X
FI - 5.0	5.0		X	X	X	X	X	X
FI - 10	10		X	X	X	X	X	X

* Catalyst load measured relatively to the mass of microcapsules.

Figure 4: Differential scanning calorimetry for fully integrated system (FI-10 pph), liquid epoxy resin – organic solvent at catalytic load of Sc(OTf)₃ (E75).

The activity of the fully integrated system (FI – 10pph) was analysed using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). A dynamic experiment from 0 – 250°C was performed for capsules crushed in a mortar and pestle, for a resin-catalyst formulation prepared separately at catalytic molar ratio (3.25 pph). It was observed that the fully integrated system exhibited high exothermal reactivity which was comparable to the liquid formulation (i.e. non-impregnated catalyst).

These studies performed herein indicated that scandium (III) triflate can be successfully impregnated onto the microcapsules surface and retain its high catalytic activity. Furthermore, poly(urea-formaldehyde) microcapsules remain stable after the impregnation, as shown in the Figure 5. Finally, the fully integrated system is capable of adhesion promotion in a short time after 1 hour at 80°C.

Figure 5: SEM images for a) single template microcapsule used in the study and b) microcapsules impregnated with $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ water solution.

3.3 Manual healing of benchmark double cantilever beam specimens

DCB test specimens were manually healed using the DGEBA – EPA resin formulation containing $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ at catalytic load (3.25 pph – 25 mmol relatively to the reactive part). Here, the focus was on defining a benchmark for the selected resin formulation. The healing agent was injected into the open crack immediately after fracture, clamped and left at 80°C until fully cured. Catalyst was not fully dissolved in order to mimic real conditions during the healing process. After 24 hours, healed DCB specimens were retested, and the average healing efficiency obtained reached 52% of the maximum peak load (Table 3). The lack of full recovery is associated with the absence of fibre bridging and the inherent brittle nature of the healing polymer. The obtained healing efficiency provides evidence that the investigated formulation exhibited good adhesion between delaminated fracture surfaces and represents great potential for implementation composite applications.

Table 2: Types of specimens tested in the study.

Designation	Healing Mechanism	Capsules load*	Catalyst load **	Catalyst location	Catalyst phase
Manual	Manual	-	3.25	Solution	Dispersion
$\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ particles	Autonomous	0.26	13.3	Dispersed	Solid
$\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ supported	Autonomous	0.26	13.3	Capsules surface	Solid

* - Capsules load was measured by mass relatively to the SA 70 epoxy resin used as the host matrix of the healing chemistries.

** - Catalyst load was calculated relatively to the mass of encapsulated reactive epoxy resin (EPON 828).

3.4 Autonomous self-healing for traditional and fully integrated systems

The self-healing of specimens containing the microcapsule – $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ particles and fully integrated healing agents was assessed using modified DCB coupon test specimens. The detailed geometry of the specimens is presented in Figure 1. The aim of this study was to demonstrate autonomous self-healing in a CFRP composite by utilising a novel fully integrated microcapsule system (FI – 10 pph) and compare it to the microcapsule – catalyst particles approach. Healing chemistries were incorporated into a central trench in DCB specimens at the identical loadings of the discrete healing resin and the catalyst.

Table 3: Recovery of initial peak load for specimens healed manually and autonomously using capsule – catalyst particles and fully integrated system (80°C for 24 hours).

Designation	Vol %	Capsules size (μm)	Initial Load	Healed Load	η (%)*	Initial G_{IC} ($\text{J}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)	Healing Temp
			P_{Virgin} (N)	P_{Healed} (N)			
Manual	-	-	47.0 \pm 1.3	24.7 \pm 4.3	52.5\pm8.9	413 \pm 19	
Sc(OTf) ₃ particles	25	20-450	57.2 \pm 10.6	5.5 \pm 1.5	9.9\pm3.5	746 \pm 97	80°C
Sc(OTf) ₃ supported	25	20-450	53.4 \pm 2.0	1.7 \pm 0.6	3.2\pm2.1	461 \pm 95	

* - Healing efficiency calculated from the difference of maximum peak load on load – displacement curves for virgin and healed specimens.

Figure 6: Representative load displacement curves for a) manually healed with E75 resin, and for b) both autonomous systems investigated.

A maximum 10% recovery was observed for specimens containing dispersed Sc(OTf)₃ particles and 3% for the fully integrated derivative composed of Sc(OTf)₃ supported on the microcapsule surface (Table 3). An increase to 14.8 \pm 9.0% was observed for specimens containing the fully integrated system after post-cure heating to 100°C for another 24 hours. It indicates that the loading of available catalyst in both investigated systems, is not enough to ensure full crosslinking of released DGEBA at the defined healing conditions (80°C for 24 hours). Moreover, lack of adhesion indicated that the thin layer of scandium (III) triflate catalyst could be poisoned by hardeners presented in the commercial resin or consumed during the curing process of the host matrix.

4 DISCUSSION

A fully integrated microcapsule – catalyst self-healing systems has been demonstrated and evaluated in a high performance CFRP composite. This system comprised of microcapsules filled with epoxy resin with scandium (III) triflate as the catalyst decorated on the microcapsules surface. Prior to embedding in a FRP, this fully integrated healing system was checked qualitatively for its ability to promote adhesion between two glass slides. The system exhibited good adhesive bonding after 1 hour at the highest supported catalyst load (FI-10pph). The heat of reaction and onset temperature recorded using DSC were similar to those found for the mixing of liquid DGEBA – discrete Sc(OTf)₃ particles. This clearly indicated that the integrated and autonomous system held potential for use as a healing function within a high performance composite material.

However, only minor load recovery was observed when this integrated system was embedded within mode I DCB specimens, which was dependent on healing temperature and time. A comparison was made of healing configurations comprising the fully integrated system and separate microcapsules as Sc(OTf)₃ particles dispersed in the polymeric matrix. Both systems tested with the same weight fraction of epoxy resin and catalyst available for repair. The maximum load recovery was found to be 3% for the integrated system and 10% for the discrete microcapsules – catalyst particle system. However, a period of prolonged heating saw an increase to 15% for the former. This low recovery

compared to a manually injected DGEBA/Sc(OTf)₃ mixture (recovery of 52% in peak load) is associated with the poor availability of catalyst. Decorating the catalyst on the microcapsule surface would appear to increase the local availability of Sc(OTf)₃ in the region of fracture. However, extended heat treatment is still needed to ensure moderate crosslinking and healing efficiency. It is surmised that the catalyst Sc(OTf)₃ is poisoned or consumed in the presence of the amine hardeners and/or epoxy resins during composite manufacture. Moreover, the amount of exposed Sc(OTf)₃ during the healing event may not be sufficient to ensure extensive crosslinking. Healing efficiency remained highly dependent on catalyst locality in the host matrix and applied healing temperature.

In summary, a fully integrated system for application in epoxy – based polymers and their composites has been demonstrated. The system has been shown to be active and adhesively bond fracture surfaces in a CFRP composite. However, premature consumption of the thin catalyst layer by the active constituents in the uncured host composite, its limited availability, brittle nature and need for heat activation are challenges that require further investigation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Microcapsules containing epoxy resin and organic solvent (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A + ethyl phenylacetate) were decorated with a smooth layer of a solid state catalyst, Sc(OTf)₃, and tested for their performance in self-healing CFRP composite laminates. Sc(OTf)₃ retains activity to initiate epoxy polymerisation after impregnation. A propensity for adhesion was demonstrated and thus the potential for implementation in an autonomous microcapsule self-healing system.

Healing efficiency was investigated using modified DCB specimens with an optimised geometry. The low availability of the catalyst following specimen cure was observed to limit healing performance. A maximum recovery in peak load of 15% was obtained after extended heat treatment for 24 hours at 100°C.

During the implementation of self-healing functionality, it has to be ensured that healing agents can be delivered to the crack plane in sufficient volume and chemical reactivity to ensure repair can take place. In the system described, the need for a solid phase catalyst has proven to be a limitation. However, the system has shown significant potential and alternative means of protecting the catalyst during processing are now being sought.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Zhnag S. Zhao Dongliang. *Aerospace Materials Handbook*. CEC Press Taylor & Francis Group 2013.
- [2] W. Binder. *Self-Healing Polymers*. WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA. 2013. Weinheim Germany.
- [3] B.J. Blaiszik, S.L.B. Kramer, S.C. Olugebefola, J.S. Moore, N.R. Sottos, S.R. White. Self-Healing Polymers and Composites, *Annual Review of Materials Research*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 179–211, Jun. 2010, (doi: 10.1146/annurev-matsci-070909-104532).
- [4] M.D. Hager, P. Greil, C. Leyens, S. van der Zwaag, U.S. Schubert. Self-healing materials., *Advanced materials (Deerfield Beach, Fla.)*, vol. 22, no. 47, pp. 5424–30, Dec. 2010, (doi: 10.1002/adma.201003036).
- [5] M. Kessler, S. White. Self-activated healing of delamination damage in woven composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 683–699, May 2001, (doi: 10.1016/S1359-835X(00)00149-4).
- [6] T.S. Coope, D.F. Wass, R.S. Trask, I.P. Bond. Metal Triflates as Catalytic Curing Agents in Self-Healing Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite Materials, *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, p. n/a–n/a, Jul. 2013, (doi: 10.1002/mame.201300026).

- [7] T.S. Coope, D.F. Wass, R.S. Trask, I.P. Bond. Repeated self-healing of microvascular carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites, *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 23, no. 11, p. 115002, Oct. 2014, (doi: 10.1088/0964-1726/23/11/115002).
- [8] B.J. Blaiszik, M.M. Caruso, D. a. McIlroy, J.S. Moore, S.R. White, N.R. Sottos. Microcapsules filled with reactive solutions for self-healing materials, *Polymer*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 990–997, Feb. 2009, (doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2008.12.040).
- [9] J. Hagen. *Concepts of Modern Catalysis and Kinetics Catalysis from A to Z*. WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA. 2006. Weinheim Germany
- [10] W.S. Precision. Standard Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites 1, vol. 01, no. Reapproved 2007, 2008.